

Teaching Readiness on 21st Century Learning: Perspectives from Primary School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This research was conducted to investigate the Islamic Education Teachers' (IET) readiness in conducting 21st-century learning style in primary schools of Kuala Kangsar District. The research was conducted by employing a quantitative approach with a survey method, which involved 140 respondents of IET serving in primary schools of Kuala Kangsar District. The data obtained were analyzed using the descriptive analysis to explain the readiness of teachers in conducting 21st-century learning. The findings revealed that the teachers had a high level of readiness ($M=3.8$, $SD=0.5$). In conclusion, the IET in the district of Kuala Kangsar is ready to accept and conduct 21st-century learning as the current method of teaching and learning in education. The teachers were identified to have high readiness to fulfill the desire for executing 21st-century learning based on the guidelines given by the Malaysian Ministry of Education. However, the teachers need to be trained and given workshops on the 21st century learning to improve their readiness and effectiveness. This is important as the teachers are the ones implementing and executing the method in their classroom.

Keywords: Readiness, Islamic Education Teachers in Primary Schools, 21st Century Learning

INTRODUCTION

In his speech during the launching of Teachers' 21st Century Learning Campaign, the former Malaysian Minister of Education, Dr. Mazlee Malik stated that the ministry introduced the 21st-century learning approach to initiate a learning environment that will be more student-centered by focusing on five elements seen as important today including communication, critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and application of moral and ethics (Sinar Harian, 2018).

These elements are seen as the basic standards in the 21st-century learning approach (Nurfaezah Mohd Hamidin & Wazzainab Ismail, 2018). It was also proposed that the

effectiveness of 21st-century learning has a great connection to the introduction of Standard Curriculum for Primary Schools (KSSR) and Standard Curriculum for Secondary Schools (KSSM) which are the main benchmarkers as intended by the Ministry of Education and Malaysian Education Blueprint (RohaniSeman, et al., 2019).

In facing the globalization era and the challenging 21st century, the teachers hold more responsibilities in instilling positive attitudes and values in youngsters as deemed by the Ministry of Education. In order to fulfill this, the role of teachers has shifted from merely teaching in classrooms to working proactively without time limit to deliver knowledge, facilitate, and mediate to the youngsters (MazarulHasanMohamadHanapi et al., 2017). Therefore, a teacher should be very thoughtful, highly skillful, talented, critical, innovative, passionate, empathic, flexible, and possess the ability to demonstrate a strong interest in education, and more importantly in facing the 21st-century challenges.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Islamic Education Teachers (IET) are the agents of change in our country's education system (Norhisham bin Muhamad&SitiHazlinibintiHaris, 2020). In other words, the changes at the school levels cannot be executed if the teachers' level of readiness is still traditional and self-centered. JahidihSaili (2015) proposed that their readiness refers to their mastery of the theoretical background and understanding of the students' learning and attitudes. Therefore, several kinds of research had been conducted to investigate the teachers' level of readiness in conducting 21st-century learning in the field of science and technology, but not many kinds of research focused on the IET (MaimunAqshaLubis et al., 2017; SalehudinSabar&Mohd Ismail Mustari, 2012). This was agreed by TarzimahTambychik&SubahanMohdMeerah (2010) who stated that many researchers focused on the practice of 21st-century learning in the mathematics and technical field. Furthermore, the study of 21st-century pedagogical practices on IET is very little done (Salehudin Sabar & Mohd Ismail Mustari, 2012).

The research conducted by Sukreni Ismail & MohdIshaAwang (2004) on the assessment of collaborative learning in Islamic Education indicated that the method was implemented on a moderate level. The Islamic Education Teachers were reported to be not ready to utilize the approach, but rather more comfortable with their traditional, 'chalk and talk' method although they were constantly sent to training on the current trend and the mentioned method to be utilized in their classrooms. UNESCO also reported that several IET was not ready to fully utilize the student-centered learning approach in their curriculum objective (MaszuriaAGhani et al., 2015). Consequently, the teaching and learning process becomes more teacher-centered, in which the students are observed to be more passive and contribute minimally to the ministry's desire; to produce progressive students.

However, Raja Abdullah & Daud Ismail (2018) stated that the teachers' readiness has a strong relation to their attitudes because they are in a symbiotic relationship with the changes in the education world. Most of the IET does not want to utilize the 21st-century learning approach because it is deemed as a form of a rebranding of the existing teaching and learning approach or pedagogy. Thus, only a small number of teachers are familiar with the 21st-century learning approach. The teachers' role is becoming more challenging as they have to strategize and facilitate to serve to their students (Ab. Halim Tamuri&NurHananiHussin, 2017). As a result of not adhering to the changes, they unwillingly become the dictators in their class as they are lacking different teaching approaches.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Specifically, the objectives of this study are:

1. Identify the Islamic Education Teachers (IET) Readiness in Mastering The Curriculum Content
2. Identify the Islamic Education Teachers (IET) Readiness in Mastering 21st Century Learning Pedagogy
3. Identify the Islamic Education Teachers (IET) Readiness in Terms of Their Attitudes
4. Identify the Islamic Education Teachers' (IET) readiness in conducting 21st-century learning.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research design is a strategy or plan used to conduct research including the procedures, data collection, and data analysis to fulfill the research purpose. This research was conducted based on a descriptive survey study to investigate the Islamic Education Teachers' level of understanding and readiness to conduct 21st-century learning in the district of Kuala Kangsar. The survey method was used to collect quantitative data pertaining to the teachers' readiness and understanding of 21st-century learning. This research involved 75 primary schools (SK) including SJK (C) and SJK (T) which operate under the supervision of the Malaysian Ministry of Education, and a total of 220 Islamic Education Teachers were reported to be serving in these schools. Based on random sampling, the researcher had chosen 152 teachers from 53 primary schools in the Kuala Kangsar district to avoid errors of unattended or partially filled-up questionnaires. As a result, from the 53 schools, a total of 148 respondents returned the questionnaires, and it was over the estimated sample size as proposed by Krejcie & Moran (1970), that is 140 respondents for a population of 220 people.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Islamic Education Teachers' readiness in conducting 21st-century learning was recorded to be at a high level with ($M=3.8$, $SD=.48$). This is further explained as their readiness in mastering the curriculum's content, 21st century's pedagogical skills, and their attitudes.

Teachers' Readiness in Mastering the Curriculum Content

Islamic Education Teachers' (IET) readiness to master the curriculum content is shown in the table below, which was on a high level ($M=3.86$, $SP=0.53$).

Table 1: Islamic Education Teachers (IET) Readiness in Mastering The Curriculum Content

Item	Min	SD	Level
I can differentiate between KBSR and KSSR curriculum	3.73	.621	High
The given DSKP is easy to understand	3.92	.612	High
I have mastered the content in the Islamic Education DSKP	3.81	.630	High
I plan the appropriate learning objectives based on students' thinking level	3.84	.816	High
I determine the teaching content based on students' ability	3.95	.638	High
I received training pertaining to the syllabus in DSKP	3.91	.640	High
Overall	3.86	0.53	High

The findings revealed the IET was ready and acknowledge the need to master the curriculum content to improve their teaching and learning method in 21st-century learning style. Aznita (2014) in her research on the Mathematics teachers' readiness in conducting Primary Schools Standard Curriculum (KSSR) in the district of Johor Bahru revealed that 94.4% of the observed sample agreed that they are aware of the development of new curriculum, and as the agent of change, they have to understand the curriculum content to make this a success. This can be seen as a result of exposing the KSSR to the teachers, before the 21st-century learning method. Therefore, the IET teachers are deemed ready to master the Islamic Education curriculum content to conduct 21st-century learning. However, it was also recorded that the teachers slightly face problems in differentiating between the Primary Schools Integrated Curriculum (KBSR) and Primary Schools Standard Curriculum (KSSR). The problem occurred when some of the teachers sent for the training to be exposed to KSSR came back to their schools and delivered the off-tangent information to their colleagues without the supervision of PPD and JPN authorities. The IET teachers were also recorded to be ready to determine the teaching content based on their students' abilities as proposed by Ab Halim & NurHanani (2017) so the planning will be able to develop and polish the students' existing potentials and skills.

Teachers' Readiness in Mastering the 21st Century Learning Pedagogy

This research also takes into account the Islamic Education Teachers' (IET) readiness to master the 21st-century learning pedagogy. The findings depicted that their level was high at (M=3.73, SD=0.50). The data are presented below:

Table 2: Islamic Education Teachers (IET) Readiness in Mastering 21st Century Learning Pedagogy

Item	Min	SD	Level
I am ready to explore the pedagogical aspect to construct effective teaching	3.81	.667	High
I am ready to attend training pertaining to the 21st-century pedagogy	3.91	.725	High
I conduct appropriate teaching method in relation to 21st-century learning	3.79	.629	High
I discuss with my colleagues to improve my pedagogical skills	3.83	.656	High
I am ready to look for suitable teaching strategies in relation to 21st-century learning	3.86	.626	High
I master the current digital literacy skills in favor of 21st-century learning	3.66	.654	Moderate
I can conduct 21st-century learning if technological resources are present	3.71	.780	High
I have the creativity to vary my teaching methods in Islamic education to support 21st-century learning	3.57	.648	Moderate
I am ready to make innovation in my 21st-century teaching and learning process	3.45	.713	Moderate
Overall	3.73	0.50	High

This research also proved that the ITE are ready to master and possess the pedagogical skills of 21st-century learning in order to conduct a contemporary teaching and learning process. ZamriMahamod (2012) supported this by stating the teachers also should possess pedagogy skills besides mastering the knowledge, and Rajendran (2001) further explained

that the teachers should have confidence in their pedagogical skills. Although IET is deemed ready to master the 21st-century pedagogical skills, there are still a small number of them hesitant to expand their creativity into innovating for 21st-century teaching. This happens as the teachers feel pressured and burdened by the amount of effort they have to put into preparing materials such as Traffic Light, Gallery Walk, Jigsaw Problem, etc., and simultaneously they also have to prepare the lesson plans on their teaching method. Nevertheless, the IET is always striving to equip themselves with the 21st century pedagogical skills as the findings revealed that the teachers are attending the training pertaining to the 21st century pedagogical skills (M=3.91, SD=0.73). This data correlates with the findings of Abdul Halim Abdullah (2017) which indicated that the mathematics teachers are passionate about gaining new knowledge about 21st-century pedagogy to improve their skills in their teaching and learning process. Another research also supports this, in which 87.4% of the teachers are willing to spend extra time to improve and expand their knowledge in order to improve their pedagogical skills (Norwati, 2012).

Teachers' Readiness in Terms of Their Attitudes

The Islamic Education Teachers' (IET) readiness in conducting the 21st-century learning also comprises of their attitudes; observed to be at a high level in this research (M=3.83, SD=0.57). A detailed explanation of this is in the table below:

Table 3: Islamic Education Teachers (IET) Readiness in Terms of Their Attitudes

Item	Min	SD	Level
I am ready to conduct 21st-century learning in my class	3.78	.647	High
I am ready to face new challenges in relation to 21st-century learning	3.84	.615	High
I am positive about the 21st-century learning method	3.79	.707	High
I am ready to make continuous changes based on 21st-century learning	3.87	.610	High
I believe in my abilities to conduct 21st-century learning	3.82	.626	High
I am interested in conducting 21st-century learning in my classroom	3.85	.688	High
I am ready to be fully committed to the implementation of 21st-century learning	3.86	.648	High
I am always flexible in facing the needs of 21st-century learning	3.79	.662	High
I accept the implementation of 21st-century learning as a means to improve the existing education system	3.90	.603	High
Overall	3.83	0.57	High

The teachers' attitudes towards the changes in the education system is another aspect that should be considered in determining their readiness to conduct 21st-century learning. In this research, the findings indicated that the teachers show positive attitudes towards the 21st-century learning process. Habib (2005) stated that a teacher should possess the knowledge and skills, accept the constantly changing curriculum, and always ready to make innovation with confidence and creativity. However, these findings are opposite of MohdIzham&Noraini's (2017) which indicated that the teachers' readiness in terms of their attitudes towards accepting the changes in the education system is rather on the moderate

level. This is because some of them are still hesitant in accepting the changes in the education field especially in relation to the implementation of information technology to elevate their teaching. The findings also suggested that the IET are ready to accept and conduct 21st-century learning to improve the process of learning. This shows that the majority of the teachers are ready to follow the changes and give continuous support to the evolving education system by changing their existing teaching methods, while some of them are still not ready.

Summary of the Islamic Education Teachers' Readiness in Conducting 21st Century Learning

It can be inferred that the Islamic Education Teachers (IET) are ready and prepared to conduct the 21st-century learning and show a positive attitude towards it as proposed by the Malaysian Ministry of Education. This proves that they are also already accepting and ready to implement 21st-Century Learning in the classroom. The findings of JaggilAppak&SuhaimiTaata (2018) well correlates with this study, in which the teachers' readiness to manage 21st-century classrooms was at a high level. Abdul Halim Abdullah (2017) reported a different view, where the teachers in secondary schools were observed to have a moderate level of readiness to utilize 21st-century learning in their classrooms. The teachers who are not ready in their teaching process are prone to influence their students' attention during the teaching and learning process (Mohammad Aziz Shah et al., 2014). Therefore, the attitudes of the teachers should be positive towards 21st-century learning and accept it as a means of positive changes for their students' success. The table below depicts the summary of the findings in this research:

Table 4: Islamic Education Teachers' (IET) readiness in conducting 21st-century learning.

Item	Min	SD	Level
Islamic Education Teachers' Readiness in Mastering the Curriculum Content	3.86	0.53	High
Islamic Education Teachers' Readiness in Mastering the 21 st Century Pedagogical Skills	3.73	0.50	High
Islamic Education Teachers' Readiness in Terms of Their Attitudes	3.83	0.57	High
Overall	3.720	0.48	High

CONCLUSION

Based on this research's findings, three important issues are deduced. Firstly, the Islamic Education Teachers (IET) have a high level of understanding of the 21st-century learning practiced in the classroom, including the concept of 21st-century learning, characteristics, and roles to be played when they are conducting and instilling various skills of 21st-century learning. Although they have a high level of understanding, it is also important for them to show interest in developing their skills. Secondly, the findings showed that their readiness to conduct the 21st-century learning strategy is significant enough in their classrooms. Even so, improvements are needed in a few aspects to maximize the success of 21st-century learning in our education system. One of the aspects that should not be underestimated is the teachers' creativity in making innovation in their teaching and learning process. Thirdly, the relationship between their understanding and level of readiness proved that the Islamic Education Teachers are truly ready to execute the 21st-century learning to fulfill the needs of quality education in Industrial Revolution 4.0 (IR 4.0). Consequently, this research hopes to be beneficial for all parties involved in the education field. The teachers' understanding and

readiness are crucial aspects as they directly result in students' performance and achievements.

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